

1 **Screening in the whole blood for bipolar disorder.**

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6 A goal of our laboratory is to develop and describe tools for use in public health detection, diagnosis and
7 prevention. Anxiety, depression and associated mental health maladies have serious consequences on
8 structure and function of society (societal composition). We describe here a set of markers derived using
9 transcriptomic methods from measurement of total transcription in healthy individuals and individuals with
10 bipolar disorder that identify bipolar disorder in the whole blood in humans.

11 Citations

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28 GSE124326